

Research Science and Innovation House

CERTIFICATE

3060-4745

Acumen: international journal of multidisciplinary research
of participation

The certificate is presented to

Xudoyorov Shaxriyor Baxtiyor o'g'li

For publication of the research article

THEME:AI YORDAMIDA TIBBIY DIAGNOSTIKANING SAMARADORLIGINI

OSHIRISH

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF
Eshkaraev S.Ch

20.05.2026

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